

LEGAL BASIS OF WATER AND WATER USE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Resume

The article deals with the rights and obligations of citizens in the process of water use, as well as problems arising in the legal regulation of relations related to water use.

Keywords: The right to use water, water consumption, consumer, objects of water use, obligation, subject, Constitution, Law on Water and Water Use.

It is known that water, which is a necessary condition for maintaining ecological balance and biological diversity, is of special importance among natural resources, in water bodies and on land.

Also, water is the most important and at the same time the cheapest natural resource in the world. However, the world's water bodies are not unlimited. Realizing this, most of the developed countries have established a sustainable use of water. On February 22, 1993, the UN General Assembly declared March 22 as World Water Day. Therefore, this date is widely celebrated every year. The ultimate goal is to enable humanity to use water efficiently and protect it, to deliver water resources to future generations in good condition. If the culture of water conservation is not widely inculcated and drastic measures are not taken to protect this resource, the situation will inevitably lead to economic, social and political problems.

Since the first years of independence in our country, the relevant legal framework for the purposeful and rational use of water resources has been created and is being put into practice.

In particular, in Article 50 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted on December 8, 1992, "Citizens are obliged to treat the environment with care", in Article 55, "water, like other natural objects, is a national wealth - the property of the state, it is necessary to use it wisely, and it must be used by the state protected"[1] is currently the legal basis for the development of water legislation and its improvement, and is considered one of the priority directions of the state water policy.

Within the framework of the subjects of relations that arise in the process of water and water use, based on the requirements of the constitution, they are defined in a number of laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan currently in force in

our country, which include the following: Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Water and Water Use", Resolution No. 82 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 19, 2013 "On the procedure for water use and water consumption in the Republic of Uzbekistan"[3] and the Regulation "On the procedure for water use and water consumption in the Republic of Uzbekistan" approved by this decision[4], Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 21, 2017 "On improving the state management system in the field of ecology and environmental protection" [5], Resolution No. 2954 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan of May 4, 2017 "On measures to regulate the rational use and accounting of underground water reserves in 2017-2021" [6], The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 25, 2017 "On measures to further improve the system of protection of water bodies" [7], The Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 16, 2017 "On measures to fundamentally improve payment discipline in the field of water supply and water extraction services" [8], Decision No. 3286 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 25, 2017 "On measures to further improve the system of protection of water bodies", The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 21, 2017 "On amendments and additions to certain legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan in connection with the strengthening of liability for violations in the field of environmental protection, rational use of natural resources, including drinking water" [9], we can include the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 9, 2019 "On measures to further improve the water resources management system" [10] and a number of other similar laws and decisions.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 6, 1993 "On Water and Water Use" consists of 29 chapters and 119 articles. The main tasks of this Law are to ensure the rational use of water for the needs of the population and economic sectors, to protect water from pollution, contamination and depletion, to prevent and eliminate the harmful effects of water, and to improve the condition of water bodies. It is also determined that it is to protect the rights and legal interests of enterprises, institutions, organizations, farmers, peasant farms and citizens in the field of water relations[2].

The main features of the water-related laws and regulatory documents adopted today in independent Uzbekistan are that they reflect modern requirements and are aimed at solving water-related problems.

However, despite this, external factors, such as climate change, violations of water use laws, and other socio-economic changes, have an increasing negative impact on the efficient use of water resources.

Therefore, a number of opinions are expressed about the adoption of the Water Code by social networks and mass media. Therefore, the adoption of the modern and international Water Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan can help solve many social and legal problems in this area.

It has been 27 years since the adoption of the Law "On Water and Water Use", many additions and amendments have been made to it, and the current demand for water resources is changing as a result of population growth, because water relations must meet the demands of a new life, a new century, and so on. demands that the water legislation should be in line with international standards"[10].

In conclusion, the legal basis of the industry in our country is regulated by some declarative norms of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Water and Water Use" and more than 20 legal documents. Therefore, there is a need to develop and introduce a comprehensive bill that is a legal basis for the rapid development of the industry.

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